

COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF OIL OF *CITRULLUS VULGARIS*, SCHRAD (WATER-MELON) SEED

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Component fatty acids of *Citrullus Vulgaris*, Schrad consist mainly of oleic and linoleic acids which are characteristic of *Cucurbitaceae* : caprylic (0.2%), capric (1.1%), lauric (0.8%), myristic (0.2%), palmitic (7.6%), stearic (6.1%), oleic (35.3%), linoleic (48.7%). Unseaponifiable matter in the oil is 0.2%

Citrullus Vulgaris, Schrad belongs to the N.O. *Cucurbitaceae* and is an annual creeper, grown abundantly in many parts of India. It is known as water-melon in English; Tarbuz or Tarmuz in Hindustani; and Hindwana in Punjabi. Its fruit is delicious and is full of watery juice. Seeds are aphrodisiac, tonic to brain, diuretic and strengthening.

No detailed study of the Indian melon-seed oil has been made in the past. Its oil is used for adulteration of the more expensive almond oil. We have found that the oil from water-melon kernels has pleasant smell and is tasteful. There seems to be no reason why it should not be used as a substitute for almond oil. Water-melon oil is reputed in Indian medicine to be nutritive and cooling on its application to head. Wehmer in his book 'Pflanzenstoffe' (1931 Edition) has mentioned that water-melon seed kernels are fairly rich in nitrogenous substances and phosphates and hence they can form a fairly good substitute for the more expensive almond kernels.

Water-melon oil is a semi-drying oil and its component fatty acids are caprylic (0.2%), capric (1.1%), lauric (0.8%), myristic (0.2%), palmitic (7.6%), stearic (6.1%), oleic (35.3%), and linoleic (48.7%). Unseaponifiable matter present in it is 0.2%. Power and Salway (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 360) reported the component fatty acids of American water-melon (*Cucurbita Citrullus*) to be linoleic (45%), oleic (25%), palmitic and stearic (30%). The composition is different from that of the present oil and it seems that the American species was of different type. Fatty acid-composition of the water-melon seed oil given by Pierserts (*Bull. Soc., Pharmacol.*, 1917, 24, 204) is 2.5% lauric, 12.6% palmitic, 15.2% stearic, 43.4% oleic and 26.3% linoleic which is different from that of the present oil. Water-melon seeds examined by Pierserts seem to be of a different species. Nolte and Loescke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 889) examined seed oil of Cuban Queen variety of water-melon and gave fatty acid composition as follows : oleic (13.03%) linoleic (68.38%), palmitic (8.84%), stearic (5.64%), archidic (0.72). They did not fractionate liquid acids and hence could not find out lower saturated acids which get dissolved in alcohol-soluble portion during lead-salt separation of mixed acids. We wish to emphasise that fractionation of liquid unsaturated acid portion is also very necessary to get correct composition. Percentage of saturated acids seems to agree somewhat but that of unsaturated acids differs from that of the Indian oil. However, total percentages of unsaturated acids agree with each other and high percentage of these acids is characteristic of *Cucurbitaceae*, as pointed out by Hilditch (*Allgem. Oel-u Fett. Ztg.*, 1930, 27, 184, 219, 255). It has been found that the fat from different species

of these seeds show some differences in composition, as in *Citrullus Pepo* (Reibsoemer and Mesty, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1784) which has 5.9% palmitic, 7.1% stearic, 40.9% oleic and 46.1% linoleic acids. Lower fatty acids (caprylic and capric) are also characteristic of the Indian water-melon seed fat, like that of melon seed fat.

Preliminary study of the glyceride structure reveals the absence of fully saturated glycerides and the presence of only 0.9% trilinolein in spite of the presence of 48.7% linoleic acids in the mixed acids. Thus it is clear that fatty acids are evenly distributed in the glycerides and it is in accordance with the theory of "even distribution of fatty acids in the seeds oil" of Hilditch (Collin and Hilditch, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 1273). From the association ratio of saturated to unsaturated acids (1 : 4.68) also, it is clear that fully saturated glycerides would not be present in the oil.

EXPERIMENTAL

Citrullus vulgaris, Schrad or water-melon seeds of red shell and not of black shell were obtained from N. W. Punjab (India) and the oil was pressed out of their kernels by cold pressing in a small press. Sediment in the oil was removed by filtration. The oil obtained is liquid at ordinary room temperature and possesses pleasant smell, agreeable taste and pale yellow colour. General characteristics of the oil along with those of West African and Cuban oils are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Particulars	<i>Citrullus Vulgaris</i> (Water-melon) kernel oil, Indian	<i>C. Vulgaris</i> (Cuban) Nolte and Loescke (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	<i>C. Vulgaris</i> (West African. Grimme- <i>Chem Zentr.</i> , 1911, 46, 1742)
Yield of oil	45.5% from kernels	26.52% from seeds	15.33% from seeds
Specific gravity	—	0.9197	0.9143
Saponification value	196.3	197.4	198.2
do equivalent	285.4	283.6	282.5
Iodine value	124.2	133.8	123.7
Acid value	5.2	6.42	—
Refractive index n_D^{20}	—	1.4669	1.4728
Unsataponifiable matter	0.3%	—	1.34%

Examination of the Fatty Acids.—The oil (250 g.) was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and mixed acids were obtained by the usual method. Acids were separated into "liquid" and "solid" fractions by the lead-salt alcohol method of separation and each fraction was converted into methyl esters which were separately fractionated under high vacuum of about 1 mm pressure. Each fraction was analysed and acids present in esters were identified (data in Table II.)

TABLE II

Mixed fatty acids :	Saponification value 268.0 and iodine value 120.8 Corresponding methyl esters	
"Liquid" (L) acids 85.4%	Saponification equivalent 281.1 (calculated 282.0)	Iodine value. 134.0 (calculated 133.0)
"Solid" (S) acids 14.6%	282.8	5.1

TABLE III

(i) Methyl ester of "Liquid" (L) acids.

No.	g.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.	No.	g.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.
L ₁	21.29	178-182	280.1	127.8	L _{1a}	6.19	163-164	276.7	118.1
					L _{1b}	6.57	164-168	282.7	132.2
					L _{1c}	2.97	168-169	281.3	136.0
					L _{1d}	0.40	Residue	280.9	136.7
L ₂	13.28	182-183	280.5	135.3					
L ₃	10.01	183-184	280.2	136.8					
L ₄	3.44	184	282.8	136.8					
L ₅	8.36	Residue	291.5	137.0					
"	Acids	Ex-N-S	282.0	142.1					
"	Esters	Ex-N-S	296.0	135.4					

(ii) Methyl esters of "Solid" (S) acids.

No.	g.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.
S ₁	3.92	160-164	277.3	3.45
S ₂	4.53	164-171	279.0	3.41
S ₃	6.23	171-175	283.8	5.96
S ₄	2.34	175	296.1	8.40

TABLE IV

Acids	Fatty acids (calculated).				
	Solid Acids 14.6%	Liquid Acids 85.4%	Including N-S	% Total fatty acids. Excluding N-S	Mols Ex N-S
Caprylic	—	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4
Capric	—	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.7
Lauric	—	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.0
Myristic	—	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
Palmitic	7.6	—	7.6	7.6	8.3
Stearic	6.1	—	6.1	6.1	5.9
Oleic	0.9	34.3	35.2	35.3	34.5
Linoleic	—	48.6	48.6	48.7	47.9
Unsaponifiable matter	—	0.2	0.2	—	—

Association ratio of saturated to unsaturated fatty acid mols is 1 : 4.68.

Identification of the Acids.—L_{1a} and L_{1b} fractions were hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and oxidised with potassium permanganate in ice-cold aqueous alkaline solution. Dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 129°) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 174°) were obtained from both of the fractions showing the presence of oleic and linoleic acids respectively.

S₁.—Dihydroxy stearic acid was obtained by oxidation of oleic acid and palmitic acid (m.p. 63°) and stearic acid (m.p. 69°) were also identified.

S₄.—The same acids as in S₁ were obtained.

Glyceride structure.—Neutral oil (100 g.) was dissolved in acetone and cooled to -5° for 4 days. No fully saturated glycerides separated. It was further oxidised by potassium permanganate but no fully saturated glycerides could be isolated.

Bromination.—Neutral oil (100 g.) was brominated in petroleum ether and the brominated products were separated into several fractions by suitable solvents. Alcohol-insoluble fractions showing the presence of trilinolein did not exceed 0.9%. Further investigation of the other glycerides present in the oil is in progress.

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